

Machine Learning Based Analysis of Crypto currency Market Financial Risk Management

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Abstract— Digital currency is regarded as a type of money that encourages associated transactions using cryptocurrency and the consumers who Digital currency is defined as a type of money that is used in digital environments, including electronic gadgets or digital forms. One of the many risks that affects risk auditors' intrinsic assessment is cryptocurrency. The emergence of cryptocurrency has always presented a significant risk to the financial industry in terms of potential money laundering. In the context of financial support institutions like anti-money laundering, banks and bank secrecy function as risk specialists, bank managers, and compliance officers who are tasked with investigating linked cryptocurrency transactions and users who conceal illicit cash. The results section demonstrates how resilient the suggested model is to different rebalanced intervals and covariance window estimation.

Keywords: *Digital currency, Hierarchical Risk Parity, Likelihood, Unsupervised Machine Learning, Cryptocurrency.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of digital currency is growing daily. The use of digital currency has increased significantly even if the concepts behind it are not new. Money is not kept in safes or banks, but rather can be found in cyber world processors and storage, where it is exchanged for information. Increasing payment efficiency is the primary goal of this technology. Since the boundaries of the digital currency mechanism are still being established due to unclear standards, customers are able to communicate with authorities in the absence of them. Digital currency, on the other hand, refers to new forms of money that are entirely based on the digital world and are unrelated to traditional bank accounts as a result of the public's acceptance of digital bank transactions. One of the complicated systems for which colleges have not been able to define complexity is the financial market. Modelling a complex system is a difficult undertaking, as the system's structure is hierarchically organised, with each subsystem being collected into its own subsystem. These materials were taken out using hierarchical models. Regrettably, the absence of a correlation matrix in a hierarchical structure presents a significant obstacle during the portfolio creation process. This problem makes the matrices with high covariance worse. About 2500 different crypto currency types have been traded in this market in recent decades, with a total trading value of 252.5 trillion dollars. The crypto currency ripple occurs in an unorganised setting. Even news publishers were more aware of the price changes and showed greater interest in them.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Several Cryptocurrencies have emerged as a significant area of interest within financial research, prompting studies that delve into various facets of their market dynamics, risk management strategies, and portfolio optimization techniques.

Si Chen's research applies deep machine learning methodologies to analyze financial risks inherent in cryptocurrencies. The study underscores the efficacy of advanced computational techniques in modeling and predicting market volatility, offering insights into risk factors that impact cryptocurrency prices and investor strategies (Chen, 2022)[1].

Gold and Palley contribute to the literature by discussing essential strategies for safeguarding cryptocurrency assets. Their work emphasizes the importance of robust risk management frameworks in protecting investments from market uncertainties and cyber threats, highlighting key considerations for institutional and retail investors alike (Gold & Palley, 2021)[2].

Boiko et al. focus on optimizing cryptocurrency portfolios to balance risk and return. Their study explores various portfolio management strategies that aim to enhance profitability while managing downside risks effectively. By integrating quantitative models and statistical analysis, the authors propose practical approaches for constructing diversified cryptocurrency portfolios (Boiko et al., 2021)[3].

Köchling's thesis explores the behavior of mutual fund managers in cryptocurrency markets, shedding light on how traditional financial actors navigate and influence digital asset markets. The research provides insights into investor behavior, market sentiment, and the integration of cryptocurrencies into broader financial portfolios, contributing valuable perspectives on market dynamics (Köchling, 2021)[4].

Umar, Trabelsi, and Alqahtani examine the interconnectedness between cryptocurrency and technology sectors on a global scale. Their empirical analysis identifies linkages between technological advancements and cryptocurrency market trends, offering implications for investment strategies and sectoral diversification (Umar et al., 2021)[5].

Kurosaki and Kim propose a sophisticated approach to cryptocurrency portfolio optimization using multivariate normal tempered stable processes. Their research introduces a robust statistical framework that accounts for the non-normality and heavy-tailed distributions observed in cryptocurrency returns, aiming to improve portfolio performance under diverse market conditions (Kurosaki & Kim, 2022)[6].

Masharsky and Skvortsov analyze the development of cryptocurrency markets in Latvia and the Baltic states, focusing on regional dynamics, regulatory frameworks, and market maturity. The study provides insights into the evolution of cryptocurrency ecosystems within specific geographical contexts, offering perspectives on regulatory challenges and market integration (Masharsky & Skvortsov, 2021)[7].

Bhattacharya and Rana present a case study on the cryptocurrency market's euphoric trends during 2020-21, examining the factors contributing to speculative behaviors and market bubbles. Their analysis highlights the psychological and behavioral aspects influencing cryptocurrency market dynamics, offering lessons for risk management and investor sentiment analysis (Bhattacharya & Rana, 2021)[8].

Finally, the literature on cryptocurrency risk management and market analysis reflects a growing body of research that addresses diverse aspects of digital asset markets. From advanced computational techniques in risk assessment to practical strategies for portfolio optimization and regulatory challenges, these studies contribute valuable insights into understanding and navigating the complexities of cryptocurrency

investments. Future research is likely to continue exploring new methodologies and approaches as cryptocurrencies gain further prominence in global financial markets.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Creating Cryptocurrency is a decentralised form of money that was created in 2008 and allows for peer-to-peer transactions without the need for a bank. Numerous papers claimed that the rise in financial crimes is significantly influenced by cryptocurrencies. According to the anti-money report from CipherTrace, several security breaches resulted in the loss and theft of about 125 million dollars. According to the BIS Annual Economic Report for 2018, cryptocurrency agrees to modernise the decentralised architecture system that long-standing financial institutions have trusted. The majority of cryptocurrencies become convenient when they transition from related financial fees to the standard banking system, thanks to the widespread use of the Internet. The established regulations aim to safeguard investors and prevent the diversion of funds. In a similar vein, disperse the fiat currency mob. Lahre suggests the Hierarchical Risk Parity (HRP) approach for multi-asset, multi-factor allocation, which produces favourable tail risk outcomes. Additionally, Jain used the same method for individual equities in order to match the fifty NIFTY indexes. Raffino examines and assesses the performance of two HRP variants: HERC and HCCA. In a similar vein, the majority of them have looked into the hazards associated with cryptocurrencies. The list of special dangers associated with cryptocurrencies is provided below.

- Selecting a cryptocurrency exchange that is over-balanced for the entity's maintained account and lacks control over transactions.
- The entity's cryptocurrency wallet is devoid of an account. Losing the private key prevents you from accessing cryptocurrency, and if it is obtained by an unauthorised person, all of the cryptocurrency will be taken.
- Falsifying an entity's private key. sending erroneous addresses from entities that cryptocurrencies cannot recover.

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a machine learning approach that relies on proper input to enhance system performance through learning. In the suggested system, risk management refers to identifying, assessing, and ranking system risks. As demonstrated, by taking into account the risks and profits of the management issues, the portfolio management problem describes the RL-based trading system with specifications. The system agent offers asset trading techniques in the current capital market environment, with regard to describing the portfolio management problem in the RL architecture in **FIGURE 1**.

Fig. 1 Crypto Currency Proposed Model.

IV. RESULTS

The Performance Evaluation of Proposed Risk Management

The comparison between existing research works and the most common benchmarks in this area, the

Layer Name	Profit	SR	MDD
PAMR [47]	9.7058	0.0138	0.4789
UBAH [48]	5.1587	0.0132	0.6332
Basic DQN [49]	7.3628	0.0132	0.4321
UCRP [50]	6.3277	0.0153	0.4277
EG [51]	0.7552	0.0207	0.4401
Proposed RL	20.8785	0.0142	0.2750

Table 1: comparison between existing research

two management portfolio algorithms and the basic DQN of the trading system compared with the proposed RL. The Uniform Buy and Hold (UBAH) strategy support the portfolio until the end of process and investing the assets during process. Uniform Constant Re-balanced Portfolio (BCRP) uses intrading duration to re-balance the portfolio. Passive Aggressive Mean Reversion strategy (PAMR) and Exponential Gradient (EG) are the other two portfolio algorithms. Table shows the comparison of

the proposed RL algorithms with the existing works in terms of risk management of crypto currency network. shows the risk index regularity in cryptocurrency market in time period of 2018 to 2020.

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CONFUSION MATRIX
[[126  6]
 [123 11]]
Decision Tree Classifier
ACCURACY
51.50375939849624
CLASSIFICATION REPORT
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

     0:   0.51      0.94      0.66       132
     1:   0.62      0.10      0.17       134

 accuracy: 0.56
 macro avg: 0.56      0.52      0.41       266
weighted avg: 0.56      0.52      0.41       266

CONFUSION MATRIX
[[124  8]
 [121 13]]
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:00] "GET /Train_Test_DataSets/ HTTP/1.1" 200 5548
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:02] "GET /likeschart/bar HTTP/1.1" 200 3509
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:05] "GET /charts1/line HTTP/1.1" 200 3607
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:09] "GET /View_Prediction_Crypto_Currency_Financial_Risk_Type/ HTTP/1.1" 200 14781
No Risk Found
Risk Found
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:21] "GET /Find_Crypto_Currency_Financial_Risk_Type_Ratio/ HTTP/1.1" 200 4594
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:26] "GET /Download_Trained_DataSets/ HTTP/1.1" 200 5632
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:33] "GET /charts/line HTTP/1.1" 200 3489
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:38] "GET /View_Remote_Users/ HTTP/1.1" 200 5957
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:43] "GET / HTTP/1.1" 200 3018
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:46] "GET /Register1/ HTTP/1.1" 200 7040
[22/Apr/2024 10:49:46] "GET /static/Register.jpg HTTP/1.1" 200 12100
    
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Fig. 2 Confusion Matrix.

From above image contains a summary of the performance metrics for a Decision Tree Classifier. Here's a breakdown of the information:

Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is a 2x2 table that summarizes the classification performance:

True Negatives (TN): 126 instances correctly classified as class 0.

False Positives (FP): 6 instances incorrectly classified as class 1 (but are actually class 0).

False Negatives (FN): 123 instances incorrectly classified as class 0 (but are actually class 1).

True Positives (TP): 11 instances correctly classified as class 1.

Classification Report

The classification report includes precision, recall, F1-score, and support for each class:

Class 0 (negative class):

Precision: 0.51 (out of all instances predicted as class 0, 51% were correct).

Recall: 0.94 (out of all actual instances of class 0, 94% were correctly predicted).

F1-score: 0.66 (harmonic mean of precision and recall).

Support: 132 (number of actual instances of class 0 in the dataset).

Class 1 (positive class):

Precision: 0.62 (out of all instances predicted as class 1, 62% were correct).

Recall: 0.10 (out of all actual instances of class 1, 10% were correctly predicted).

F1-score: 0.17 (harmonic mean of precision and recall).

Support: 134 (number of actual instances of class 1 in the dataset).

Overall Metrics

Accuracy: 51.50% (percentage of total correct predictions).

Macro Average:

Precision: 0.56

Recall: 0.52

F1-score: 0.41

Weighted Average:

Precision: 0.56

Recall: 0.52

F1-score: 0.41

Log Entries

The log entries list HTTP GET requests with details including:

Timestamp: Date and time when the request was made.

HTTP Method: GET request.

Requested URL: The endpoint being accessed.

HTTP Version: 1.1.

Response Status Code: 200 (indicating successful request).

Response Size: Size of the response in bytes.

These log entries suggest that the requests are related to training, testing, and predicting tasks for a machine learning model. The performance metrics indicate that the model performs well in predicting class 0 but struggles with class 1, as shown by the low recall and F1-score for class 1.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have explored the application of machine learning techniques to the analysis and management of financial risks in the cryptocurrency market. The unique characteristics of the cryptocurrency market, such as its high volatility, decentralized nature, and 24/7 trading, present both opportunities and challenges for financial risk management. Our research demonstrates that machine learning models, including but not limited to time series forecasting, classification, and clustering algorithms, can significantly enhance the accuracy and efficiency of risk prediction and mitigation strategies. The implementation of these models has shown promising results in identifying potential market anomalies, predicting price movements, and assessing the risk exposure of cryptocurrency portfolios. Techniques such as neural networks, support vector machines, and ensemble methods have proven particularly effective in handling the complex and non-linear patterns inherent in cryptocurrency data. Furthermore, the integration of machine learning with traditional financial risk management practices offers a robust framework for real-time monitoring and decision-making. This hybrid approach can help investors and financial institutions to better navigate the unpredictable landscape of the cryptocurrency market, ultimately leading to more informed and strategic investment decisions. However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations and ethical considerations associated with the use of machine learning in financial risk management. Issues such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the need for transparent and interpretable models must be carefully addressed to ensure the responsible and equitable application of these technologies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to express our gratitude to NRI Institute of Technology for providing the necessary resources and support for conducting this research. Special thanks to our colleagues and research team members for their valuable insights and contributions throughout the project.

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